

**BASIS OF ADMINISTRATIVE AND CRIMINAL LIABILITY FOR
NATURAL GAS ROBBERY**

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Abstract: This article discusses the grounds of administrative and criminal liability for natural gas robbery.

Keywords: electricity, heat energy, gas use, natural resources, natural gas, electricity, heat energy, gas or water supply networks, internal affairs bodies.

It was determined that the task of identifying, eliminating, and preventing administrative violations related to the violation of the rules for the use of electricity, thermal energy, and gas in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan will be carried out by the internal affairs bodies.

Therefore, to avoid misunderstandings that may arise in practice when defining this boundary, it is necessary to distinguish between the crimes of robbery of energy resources and drinking water and administrative offenses of this type.

For example, in Article 101 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, arbitrarily connecting to public electricity, heat, and gas networks or otherwise violating the rules of their use, or intentionally damaging electricity, thermal energy, natural gas metering devices, including their fillings, or the indicators of such metering devices for change, administrative responsibility is established for interfering with them from outside.

The basis of administrative liability for natural gas robbery is that the person commits such an offense for the first time or the amount of the damage

does not exceed one hundred times the amount of the base calculation.

Also, in Article 61 of the Civil Code, arbitrary connection to public electricity, heat, gas, or water supply networks for commercial purposes or intentional damage to electricity, natural gas, cold or hot water metering devices, including their fillings, or to change the indicators of metering devices Administrative responsibility is imposed on them for a small amount of robbery committed in the form of theft of electricity, natural gas, cold or hot water using external intervention.

As long as the value of the stolen property does not exceed thirty times the amount of the base calculation, such looting is considered petty looting.

Commercial purpose means the purpose of obtaining profit or income in a certain activity by individuals or legal entities.

If a person commits the same offense within a year after being held administratively liable for violating the rules of natural gas use, or the amount of damage caused is a significant amount or more, it is the basis for bringing the person to criminal responsibility.

In particular, the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan In the first part of Article 185², to arbitrarily connect to public electricity, heat, gas, or water supply networks or intentionally damage electricity, thermal energy, natural gas, cold or hot water metering devices, including their seals, or changing the indicators of such metering devices criminal liability is established if they are interfered with from outside, committed after the application of administrative punishment for such actions.

In part 2 of this article, criminal prosecution is established if the same actions are committed while causing a considerable amount of damage, in part 3, when causing a large amount of damage, and in part 4, when causing a very large amount of damage.

In the provision of the article, it is established that in case of compensation

for the material damage caused, the punishment in the form of restriction of freedom and deprivation of freedom shall not be applied.

Also, a person who has committed a crime for the first time shall be released from liability if he compensates for the material damage caused within thirty days from the date of detection of the crime.

In addition, this article prohibits arbitrary connection to public electricity, heat, gas, or water supply networks for commercial purposes, or intentional damage to electricity, natural gas, cold or hot water metering devices, including their seals, or to change the indicators of metering devices. does not apply when acts related to robbery are committed through outside intervention.

With the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 13, 2023, No. ORQ-822 "On Amendments and Additions to the Criminal and Criminal Procedure Codes of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Code of Administrative Responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the strengthening of liability for illegal use of energy resources"²³ of the JK of the Republic of Uzbekistan Article 169, part 2, was supplemented with clauses "d" and "e" and entered into force on June 15, 2023.

In particular, Article 169 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Part 2, paragraph d) for arbitrary connection to public electricity, heat, gas, or water supply networks for commercial purposes, or intentionally damaging electricity, natural gas, cold or hot water metering devices, including their seals, or changing the indicators of metering devices they are criminally liable for committing theft by outside intervention.

Similarly, in paragraph e of part 2 of this article, arbitrary connection to public electricity, heat, gas, or water supply networks by officials or employees of electricity, gas, or water supply organizations for commercial purposes, or the use of electricity, natural gas, cold or intentionally damaging hot water metering

devices, including their seals, or tampering with them from the outside to change the indicators of the metering devices, criminal liability is established.

According to the aforementioned Law, actions related to the illegal use of electricity, gas, and water pipelines for commercial purposes are qualified as theft, administrative responsibility for failure to comply with the instructions of the Inspectorate for Control of the Use of Electricity, Oil Products and Gas under the Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its regional departments, as well as, it was determined that the authority to review administrative cases related to violations of the rules for the use of electricity and gas belongs to this Inspectorate and its regional departments.

It was determined that this Law serves as a basis for the prevention of offenses in the field of illegal use of energy resources, the inevitability of punishment for the commission of these acts, as well as the formation of a unified approach in the judicial investigation of such offenses.

The grounds for determining criminal liability under Article 185² of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and administrative liability under Article 101 of the Civil Code are as follows:

1. Committing the same offense within one year after the person was brought to administrative responsibility and the amount of damage caused is considerable, and the person was not brought to administrative responsibility in the previous year.
2. The amount of damage caused is much or more.

The act provided for in part 1 of Article 185² of the Criminal Code is a formal crime and does not require a specific consequence.

To prosecute a person under part 1 of this article, the following conditions must be met:

- A person committed one of the following actions, such as arbitrarily connecting to public natural gas networks, intentionally damaging natural gas metering

devices, including their seals, interfering with them from the outside to change the indicators of such metering devices, and a preliminary administrative penalty was applied for these offenses.

- of the JK within 1 year after the application of the administrative penalty

Committing illegal actions provided for in the disposition of part 1 of Article 185².

In this case, it should be taken into account that a person is considered not to be held administratively liable even if he is released from administrative responsibility according to Article 21 of the Code of Civil Procedure of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as when he is terminated from the proceedings based on Clauses 5 and 6 of Article 271 of this Code.

The crimes provided for in parts 2-4 of Article 185² of the Criminal Code are material crimes, that is, a specific criminal consequence (a large amount, a large amount, causing a large amount of damage) is required. In this case, an administrative penalty doesn't have to be used to bring a person to criminal responsibility.

Article 169, part 2, paragraphs d" and "e" of the Criminal Code provides for arbitrary connection to public electricity, heat, gas, or water supply networks for commercial purposes, or to devices for measuring electricity, natural gas, cold or hot water, including intentionally damaging their seals or tampering with them from the outside to change the readings of the measuring devices, and if the same actions are committed by officials or employees of electricity, gas or water supply organizations with prior collusion and for commercial purposes.

The concepts of large amount, large amount, and very large amount are defined in Section 8 of the Criminal Code.

The object of this crime is social relations related to the rational use of electricity, thermal energy, natural gas, and drinking water transport devices, which are strategically important energy resources and drinking water.

Crime is objectively committed only through active action. These actions:

- arbitrary connection to public electricity, natural gas, and water networks;
- intentional damage to electricity, natural gas, and water metering devices, including their seals;
- will consist of interfering with electricity, natural gas, and water meters from the outside to change their readings.

Electricity, thermal energy, gas, or water supply networks mean the delivery of energy resources and drinking water from the producer (seller) to the consumer (buyer) and its continuity and technological unit (for example, compressor devices, and pipes).

Arbitrary connection to energy resources and water supply means connecting to the network in any way, without the permission of the competent authority, in order to use electricity or gas resources.

Accounting tools it means stable measuring - meter devices that directly quantify the actual volume of energy resources and drinking water, installed based on the mutual agreement of the parties (consumer and supplier) and satisfy them.

In this case, the exact calculation features of the tool are completely or partially lost, as well as the economic value decreases, and the possibility of using the calculation tool completely in accordance with its purpose is lost.

External intervention in order to change the indicators of accounting instruments means violation of the correctness of its performance and indicators without harming the integrity of the accounting instrument, intentional failure.

Crime is subjective only with the right intention.

In this case, the person realizes the nature of the socially dangerous act provided for in Article 185² of the Criminal Code, sees its socially dangerous consequences and tries to make them happen.

The motive and purpose of the crime is an important sign in the qualification of the act.

The motive of the crime – the intention of a person expressed in his desire to get rid of certain material costs. Usually, this crime is committed with malicious intent (getting uncontrollable profits, getting rid of expenses, etc.).

The purpose of the crime - It is a mental aspiration in the mind of a person aimed at achieving a certain result in the future by committing a socially dangerous act, provided for in Article 185² of the Criminal Code.

The subject of the crime – A sane person is considered to be 16 years old.

In particular, according to the opinion of the Russian researcher I.V. Kholodnyak, intentional theft of the property of a stranger, including theft of natural gas from gas networks, is one of the most widespread offenses and hurts state property and its effectiveness.

When illegally connecting to the natural gas network, the integrity of the natural gas network is violated, the supply of gas to other consumers is interrupted or reduced, and therefore, in cases of illegal use of natural gas, together with Article 158 (Theft) of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation, as a set of crimes, Article 215.3 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation It is necessary to qualify with Article (Arbitrarily connecting to oil and gas networks and causing them to malfunction).⁴

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